

PRAGMATISM VIS-À-VIS THE LEARNING EXPERIENCES OF BEED STUDENTS IN THE MIDST OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

This research paper sought to describe how evident the principles in pragmatism are in the experiences of BEEd teacher education students of CTE-BatStateU-Pablo Borbon. This described the teaching-learning activities in terms of nature, methods/ processes; modes of assessment. The usefulness and practicality of the teaching – learning activities were also determined for the purpose of providing interventions and enhancements in the flexible learning modality of the College. The descriptive study utilized online survey questionnaire to gather data. It was found that the BEEd students assessed that nature of teaching-learning activities to be considerate and based on their needs of the future teachers as well their situation, with individualized learning modules and combination of blended learning. The students' learning is assessed through objective and outcomes based modes of evaluation. The students also revealed that the activities provided to them are useful and contributory to their future roles as educators indicating that the respondents learned the skills and knowledge needed by a 21st century educator. In general, the respondents revealed that the College provided practical and utilitarian activities during the COVID-19 pandemic. Proposed interventions and enhancements provided as output of the study. It was concluded that the teaching learning activities are individualized, needs- based, flexible, practical, useful and contributory to the future profession of the respondents.

Keywords: a. Education; b. pragmatism, COVID-19; teaching profession; c. descriptive; d. Philippines